

Pan-genome Analysis of Plastids from Caryophyllales

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Abstract

A comparative analysis of plastid sequences from the Caryophyllales order is performed using the Pangenome Research Toolkit (PGR-TK). Overall, most genera and families showed high degrees of uniformity. At the genus level, *Arenaria* and *Drosera* diverged most from the general conserved pattern. Additionally, *Dysphania*, *Caroxylon*, *Portulaca*, *Salsola*, *Stellaria* and *Suaeda* had higher levels of divergence than most genera. At the family level, phylogeny generated by PGR-TK correctly separated the genera. Other than Cactaceae and Droseraceae, all family level plots were relatively uniform.

Introduction

The order Caryophyllales, within the superasterid clade of eudicots, encompasses a diverse range of flowering plants adapted to various environments, including hot, cold, arid, saline, and disturbed habitats [1, 2]. This large order, comprising approximately 12,500 species, includes both economically important plants, such as beet, amaranth, bougainvillea, carnation, spinach, chard, and celosia, and a wide array of other species, including cacti, succulents, and carnivorous plants. The Caryophyllales order plays a crucial role in understanding the evolution of flowering plants, particularly because of the variety of climates and ecological niches it occupies, offering valuable insights into plant adaptation and diversification.

Molecular phylogenetic studies of the Caryophyllales order currently recognize 42 families [3], including several well-known plant families such as Caryophyllaceae (the pink or carnation family), Amaranthaceae (the amaranth family), Polygonaceae (the buckwheat family), Cactaceae (the cactus family) and Portulacaceae (the purslane family). Due to the remarkable diversity within this order, considerable variation is observed among species, leading to ongoing debates regarding the classification and placement of genera and families. Several methods were applied to determine the phylogenetic classification of the families and genera within this order ranging from comparing individual genes like 18S rDNA, rbcL, atpB, and matK to analyzing entire transcriptomes [3-9]. Phylogenetic research also aims to distinguish between core and non-core families within Caryophyllales.

Recently it has become possible to obtain numerous complete plastid sequences from this order due to advancements in sequencing technologies and rapidly decreasing costs. This progress now makes it possible to analyze entire genomes, including pan-genome studies. The Pangenome Research Toolkit (PGR-TK), a recently published tool, uses a minimizer-based approach to significantly improve processing speed for genome comparison [10]. This approach enables comprehensive comparisons of entire plastid genomes and offers visual representations of similarity blocks, providing valuable insights into the evolutionary relationships among the families studied. Earlier we demonstrated the effectiveness of PGR-TK for analyzing plastids [11, 12], and here, we applied it to the 31 genera and 13 families within Caryophyllales for which complete plastid sequences were available.

Results and Discussions

Plastid sequences were downloaded from NCBI and split into FASTA files, each containing sequences of the individual genera. The 31 genera included *Achyranthes* (3 sequences), *Amaranthus* (14), *Arenaria* (3), *Atraphaxis* (4), *Atriplex* (5), *Beta* (10), *Bougainvillea* (13), *Caroxylon* (3), *Cerastium* (4), *Ceratostigma* (5), *Chenopodium* (8), *Colobanthus* (8), *Dianthus* (8), *Drosera* (4), *Dysphania* (3), *Eremogone* (5), *Gypsophila* (5), *Limonium* (6), *Myricaria* (8), *Nepenthes* (3), *Opuntia* (29), *Patellifolia* (3), *Phytolacca* (10), *Portulaca* (4), *Pseudostellaria* (9), *Salicornia* (5), *Salsola* (3), *Silene* (31), *Stellaria* (3), *Suaeda* (5), and *Tamarix* (10). These genera were analyzed with PGR-TK to identify conservation amongst sequences. Additionally, analysis was run at the family level on 13 Caryophyllales families.

By inputting FASTA formatted files into PGR-TK, we were able to analyze differences and similarities in plastid sequences of various species. Because plastid sequences are circular, the sequences had to be rotated to have the same starting point. This allowed for more accurate analysis of the different genera. Many plastid genomes contain two inverted repeat regions (IR), a large copy region (LSC), and a small copy region (SSC). After running pgr-pbundle-decomp, we were able to analyze the plots and cladograms of different species of genera in the Caryophyllales order. Detailed methods are available in Ref 12.

Observations at the Genus Level

Most often, four unique segments within the plastid sequences are noticeable in the -TK plots representing the long single-copy (LSC) regions, short single-copy (SSC) regions, and two inverted repeat (IR) regions. Both IR regions identified by PGR-TK are displayed with the same color. Typically sequences of the same genus are of similar lengths.

Occasionally, the genus level plots diverge from this expected pattern. Reference 12 outlines five broad classes of patterns seen among plastid sequences at the genus level, namely pattern 1 - clear quadripartite plastome structures, pattern 2 - highly fragmented conserved segments, pattern 3 - misclassification of plant genus, pattern 4 - short sequences primarily from parasitic plants and pattern 5 - a combination of unconventional patterns. All Caryophyllales genera fall within one or more of these listed pattern classes (Table 1).

(i) *Achyranthes*, *Amaranthus*, *Atraphaxis*, *Atriplex*, *Beta*, *Bougainvillea*, *Caroxylon*, *Cerastium*, *Ceratostigma*, *Chenopodium*, *Colobanthus*, *Dianthus*, *Eremogone*, *Gypsophila*, *Limonium*, *Myricaria*, *Nepenthes*, *Patellifolia*, *Phytolacca*, *Pseudostellaria*, *Salicornia*. All sequences showed uniform length and conserved IRs (Fig. 1).

(ii) *Arenaria*, *Drosera*, *Dysphania*, *Caroxylon*, *Portulaca*, *Salsola*, *Stellaria*, *Suaeda*. *Arenaria* and *Drosera* exhibited extreme fragmentation, no identifiable IRs (Fig 2). The others showed small, fragmented segments (tiny rectangles) suggesting high divergence.

(iv) *Tamarix* included one notable short sequence potentially due to a sequencing error.

(v) *Opuntia*, *Silene*. *Opuntia* showed simple plastome structures but varied in length. *Silene* exhibited sequences with varying lengths.

Observations at the Family Level

Thirteen families within Caryophyllales have family level plastid data available. They are described below.

Caryophyllaceae

Let us start by examining Caryophyllaceae, a large family with several genera [13-16]. The major genera include *Dianthus*, *Gypsophila*, *Silene*, *Pseudostellaria*, and *Stellaria*, with numerous smaller genera such as *Eremogone*, *Perochia*, and others. The sequences for each genus appear to cluster neatly. Most genera are well-separated, with the exception of *Agrostemma*, which is included within *Silene*. There are two distinct groups of *Silene* likely due to inversion of SSC relative to LSC.

Overall, the sequences separate into multiple groups. The first group includes *Dianthus*, *Gypsophila*, and *Petrohragia*, which cluster together. Close to these is *Colobanthus*. Another large group consists of *Pseudostellaria* and *Stellaria*. At the bottom, a massive group is made up of various *Silene* species, along with a number of smaller genera that remain separate.

In terms of sequence length, most are quite similar, with a few exceptions. A small group of sequences from *Eremogone* stands out, as does one sequence from *Arenaria*, which appears within *Eremogone* (Fig 3). The presence of this sequence warrants further investigation, especially since another *Arenaria* sequence is more distantly related.

As for sequence conservation, a small conserved region in all sequences corresponding to an inverted repeat is observed.

Amaranthaceae

The Amaranthaceae family also consists of multiple genera, with the largest being *Amaranthus* and *Beta*. Again, the sequences group according to genus, though there are cases where multiple genera cluster together. Notably, all sequences share a similar length and include a conserved region from the inverted repeat.

Compared to Caryophyllaceae, the sequences in Amaranthaceae show greater uniformity, with Amaranthaceae appearing more conserved overall.

Cactaceae

The Cactaceae family has a variety of sequences, with *Opuntia* dominating. A notable feature is that *Opuntia* sequences split into two different length groups, which raises the possibility of divergence amongst the genus (Fig 4). The plot includes other genera as well, and they exhibit considerable variation in sequence length.

The sequence conservation in Cactaceae is not as strong as in the previous two families. The outermost clade exhibits low conservation and a variety of genera, standing apart from *Opuntia*. The genera *Airampoa*, *Brasiliopuntia*, and *Tacinga* seem misplaced. Most conservation is seen within the *Opuntia* sequences, despite being split into two separate clades.

Nyctaginaceae

Nyctaginaceae is a smaller family compared to the previous ones, with most of the plants being *Bougainvillea* and a few other smaller genera. Other genera including *Pisonia*, *Miribalis*, *Acleisanthes*, *Boerhavia*, and *Nyctaginia* show similar conservation to *Bougainvillea*. However, one *Bougainvillea* sequence appears in the outermost clade and is separated from the main group of *Bougainvillea* due to its inversion of SSC from the LSC. Additionally, the lengths of the sequences are quite uniform.

Plumbaginaceae

The Plumbaginaceae family consists of just three genera. The sequences can be grouped into two distinct clusters. One group includes *Limonium*, which stands apart from the other group that contains *Ceratostigma* and *Plumbago*. Differences in sequence similarity and length are evident between these groups (Fig 5). Furthermore, although genus level plots show *Ceratostigma ulicinum* to be more closely related to *C. plumbaginoides* and *C. willmottianum*, family level analysis shows *Ceratostigma ulicinum* as the most distant, grouped with *Plumbago*.

Droseraceae

Droseraceae [17] exhibits extensive sequence variation. In addition to *Drosera*, this family includes sequences from *Aldrovanda* and *Dionaea*. It shows a remarkable degree of sequence diversity, with no apparent conserved blocks visible in the sequence plot (Fig 6).

Tamaricaceae

The Tamaricaceae family primarily contains sequences from *Tamarix*, with one exception: a sequence from *Reaumuria*, which stands out due to its difference with the other sequences. While the rest of the sequences are quite conserved, *Tamarix androssowii* appears much shorter than the rest of the *Tamarix* genera.

Aizoaceae

Aizoaceae [18] is a small family with only five plant sequences from three different genera: *Mesembryanthemum*, *Tetragonia*, and *Sesuvium*. While the inverted repeats are conserved, noticeable divergence is observed outside of that region, despite the small number of sequences.

Montiaceae

Similar to Aizoaceae, Montiaceae also contains five sequences, though the genera here are slightly different: *Cistanthe* (two sequences), *Calandrinia* (two sequences), and *Montia* (one sequence). There is conservation in the inverted repeats and is generally conserved outside of this region.

Petiveriaceae

Petiveriaceae contains four sequences from four different genera. The sequences appear well conserved with minor divergence outside the inverted repeat regions.

Phytolaccaceae, Portulacaceae, Nepenthaceae

The remaining families are composed of a single genus. Therefore, the family-level plots did not provide any additional insight. Among these, *Phytolacca* and *Nepenthes* show a relatively uniform sequence pattern. However, *Portulaca* exhibits noticeable sequence diversity, though the inverted repeats are still identifiable.

Figures

Figure 1: PGR-TK plot of the *Amaranthus* genus. The sequences are well conserved across the *Amaranthus* genus.

Figure 2: PGR-TK plot of the *Drosera* genus. The sequences show varied sequence lengths and extreme variation, no identifiable IR region.

Figure 5: PGR-TK plot of the Plumbaginaceae family. *Limonium* exhibits different conservation patterns.

Figure 6: PGR-TK Plot of the Droseraceae family. This plot is highly fragmented with diverse sequence patterns and no well conserved regions.

Tables

Genus	Family	Pattern Class (based on Ref 12)	Comments
Achyranthes	Amaranthaceae	1	
Amaranthus	Amaranthaceae	1	
Arenaria	Caryophyllaceae	2	Highly fragmented
Atraphaxis	Polygonaceae	1	
Atriplex	Amaranthaceae	1	
Beta	Amaranthaceae	1	
Bougainvillea	Nyctaginaceae	1	
Caroxylon	Amaranthaceae	2	Tiny fragmented segments
Cerastium	Caryophyllaceae	1	
Ceratostigma	Plumbaginaceae	1	
Chenopodium	Amaranthaceae	1	
Colobanthus	Caryophyllaceae	1	
Dianthus	Caryophyllaceae	1	
Drosera	Droseraceae	2	Highly fragmented
Dysphania	Amaranthaceae	2	Tiny fragmented segments
Eremogone	Caryophyllaceae	1	

Gypsophila	Caryophyllaceae	1	
Limonium	Plumbaginaceae	1	
Myricaria	Tamaricaceae	1	
Nepenthes	Nepenthaceae	1	
Opuntia	Cactaceae	5	Simple structure, varied lengths
Patellifolia	Amaranthaceae	1	
Phytolacca	Phytolaccaceae	1	
Portulaca	Portulacaceae	2	Tiny fragmented segments
Pseudostellaria	Caryophyllaceae	1	
Salicornia	Amaranthaceae	1	
Salsola	Amaranthaceae	2	Tiny fragmented segments
Silene	Caryophyllaceae	5	Sequences with varying lengths
Stellaria	Caryophyllaceae	1	
Suaeda	Amaranthaceae	2	Tiny fragmented segments
Tamarix	Tamaricaceae	4	One short sequence

Table 1. PGR-TK Patterns of Genera within Caryophyllales. This table summarizes the patterns observed among various PGR-TK plots from 30 genera of Caryophyllales. The pattern classes are described in Ref [12]. Additional comments are provided for some genera.

References

1. Caryophyllales [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jul 3]. Available from: <https://www.mobot.org/MOBOT/research/APweb/orders/caryophyllalesweb.htm#Caryophyllales>
2. Hernández-Ledesma P, Berendsohn WG, Borsch T, Mering SV, Akhani H, Arias S, et al. A taxonomic backbone for the global synthesis of species diversity in the angiosperm order Caryophyllales. *Willdenowia*. 2015 Sep;45(3):281.

3. An update of the Angiosperm Phylogeny Group classification for the orders and families of flowering plants: APG IV. *Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society*. 2016 Mar 24;181(1):1–20.
4. Cuénoud P, Savolainen V, Chatrou LW, Powell M, Grayer RJ, Chase MW. Molecular phylogenetics of Caryophyllales based on nuclear 18S rDNA and plastid *rbcL*, *atpB*, and *matK* DNA sequences. *American Journal of Botany*. 2002 Jan;89(1):132–44.
5. Brockington SF, Alexandre R, Ramdial J, Moore MJ, Crawley S, Dhingra A, et al. Phylogeny of the Caryophyllales *Sensu Lato*: Revisiting Hypotheses on Pollination Biology and Perianth Differentiation in the Core Caryophyllales. *International Journal of Plant Sciences*. 2009 Jun;170(5):627–43.
6. Brockington SF, Walker RH, Glover BJ, Soltis PS, Soltis DE. Complex pigment evolution in the Caryophyllales. *New Phytologist*. 2011 Mar 18;190(4):854–64.
7. Smith SA, Brown JW, Yang Y, Bruenn R, Drummond CP, Brockington SF, et al. Disparity, diversity, and duplications in the Caryophyllales. *New Phytologist*. 2017 Sep 11;217(2):836–54.
8. Walker JF, Yang Y, Feng T, Timoneda A, Mikenas J, Hutchison V, et al. From cacti to carnivores: Improved phylotranscriptomic sampling and hierarchical homology inference provide further insight into the evolution of Caryophyllales. *American Journal of Botany*. 2018 Mar;105(3):446–62.
9. Yao G, Jin JJ, Li HT, Yang JB, Mandala VS, Croley M, et al. Plastid phylogenomic insights into the evolution of Caryophyllales. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*. 2019 May;134:74–86.
10. Chin CS, Behera S, Khalak A, Sedlazeck FJ, Sudmant PH, Wagner J, et al. Multiscale analysis of pangenomes enables improved representation of genomic diversity for repetitive and clinically relevant genes. *Nature Methods*. 2023 Jun 26;20(8):1213–21.
11. Jayanti R, Kim A, Pham S, Raghavan A, Sharma A, Samanta MP. arXiv.org. 2023. Comparative Analysis of Plastid Genomes Using Pangenome Research ToolKit (PGR-TK). Available from: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2310.19110>
12. Samanta MP. arXiv.org. 2025. Pan-genome Analysis of Angiosperm Plastomes using PGR-TK. Available from: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.20034>
13. Heubl G, Bringmann G, Meimberg H. Molecular Phylogeny and Character Evolution of Carnivorous Plant Families in Caryophyllales — Revisited. *Plant Biology*. 2006 Nov;8(6):821–30.
14. Greenberg AK, Donoghue MJ. Molecular systematics and character evolution in Caryophyllaceae. *TAXON*. 2011 Dec;60(6):1637–52.
15. Smissen RD, Clement JC, Garnock-Jones PJ, Chambers GK. Subfamilial relationships within Caryophyllaceae as inferred from 5' *ndhF* sequences. *American Journal*

of Botany. 2002 Aug;89(8):1336–41.

16. Hoang TT, Le LB, Le NTK, Nguyen MTA, Truong ATL, Tran NT, et al. Molecular phylogeny and cryptic morphology: A combined approach to taxonomic novelties in *Polycarpaea* (Caryophyllaceae) from Vietnam. PLOS ONE. 2024 Oct 16;19(10):e0301407.

17. Rivadavia F, Kondo K, Kato M, Hasebe M. Phylogeny of the sundews, *Drosera* (Droseraceae), based on chloroplast *rbcl* and nuclear 18S ribosomal DNA Sequences. American Journal of Botany. 2003 Jan;90(1):123–30.

18. Klak C, Hanáček P, Bruyns PV. Phylogeny and reclassification of *Lampranthus* (Ruschieae, Aizoaceae) in southern Africa. TAXON. 2024 May 12;73(3):818–53.